

Studies in Furan Derivatives: Part VI. Synthesis of 1,7-Dimethylnaphtho (2, 1-b : 7, 6-b') difuran

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A number of naphtho difurans have been synthesised by Kuriakose and Sethna¹ and by Dingankar *et al*². from the different dihydroxynaphthalenes by different methods. We now report the synthesis of 1,7-dimethylnaphtho(2,1-b; 7,6-b') difuran (I) starting with 2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene. 2,7-Diacetoxynaphthalene on Fries migration at 140° in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride gave a diacetyl derivative which was also obtained from 2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene on Friedel-Crafts acetylation using acetyl chloride and anhydrous aluminium chloride. The diacetyl derivative gave a violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It was however, very sparingly soluble in the usual solvents and its NMR spectra was therefore not satisfactory. The diacetyl derivative could have any of the three structures : 1,6-; 1,8- or 3,6-diacetyl-2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene. Its structure was found to be 2,7-dihydroxy-1,6-diacetylnaphthalene on the basis of the NMR spectra of the difuran derivative synthesised from it as follows : The diacetyl dihydroxynaphthalene was condensed with bromoacetic ester in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone solution. The 2,7-bis(carbethoxymethoxy)naphthalene derivative thus obtained was hydrolysed with alkali to the corresponding acid which on simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gave the difuran derivative. Its NMR spectra in deuterated chloroform showed signals at 488 and 506 cps which favours the structure (I), as this would have 2 aromatic proton singlets in addition to furan proton singlets.

I

EXPERIMENTAL

2,7-Diacetoxynaphthalene : 2,7-Dihydroxynaphthalene (2 g.) was mixed with acetic anhydride (15 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (4 g.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed gently on a wire gauze for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product which separated on pouring the reaction mixture in cold water was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 132°. (Found : C, 69.0; H, 5.2. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.9%).

1,6-Diacetyl-2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene : An intimate mixture of 2,7-diacetoxynaphthalene (2 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 140° for 4 hr. The product which separated on decomposition of the reaction mixture with ice and hydrochloric acid was crystallised from benzene in reddish yellow needles (1 g.), m.p. 152°. It gave a dark violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 69.1; H, 5.1. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 68.9; H, 4.9%).

The same product was obtained in a lower yield when a mixture of 2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene (1.5 g.), acetyl chloride (3 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 120° for 3 hr. and the reaction mixture was worked up as usual.

1,6-Diacetyl-2,7-bis-(carbethoxymethoxy)naphthalene : The above diacetyl derivative (1 g.) in acetone was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. with ethylbromoacetate (1.2 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.5 g.). The product obtained on removal of acetone and addition of water crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 112°. Yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 63.6; H, 5.9. $C_{12}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 63.5; H, 5.8%).

1,6-Diacetyl-2,7-bis (carboxymethoxy) naphthalene : The above ester (1 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide (10 ml.; 5%) on a water bath at 60° till a clear solution was obtained. This was kept overnight and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product which separated was purified through sodium bicarbonate solution and then crystallised from acetic acid in reddish brown needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 230° (decomp.). (Found : C, 60.1; H, 4.3. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 69.0; H, 4.4%).

1,7-Dimethylnaphtho(2,1-b; 7,6-b')difuran : The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) on a sand bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in water and the separated product washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then crystallised from alcohol in yellow plates (0.3 g.), m.p. 103°. (Found : C, 80.9; H, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 81.4; H, 5.1%).

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